

The Peace Path: Buddha Path

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ABSTRACT

Since their very existence, human beings have gone through many sweet and sour experiences to organize their life and make them better. In this process, they have been collecting and assimilating sweet essences and distancing themselves from the bad elements. In the course of this excellent development, they have been struggling with many sorrows and have always been trying to get rid of them. Thousands of unsung great minds have made the world a better place. Peace has remained an essential condition of human civilization, especially since the beginning of mutual conflicts between individuals. Throughout the vast span of human civilization, spanning millions of years, it has been destroyed many times, and this destruction continues to this day. The search for peace and the solution to freedom from suffering was discovered for the first time in a systematic manner in the world, and it was by Buddha. He has proved to be the first true researcher of this world. This is the reason why the whole world today considers Buddha as the ideal researcher of peace. Every developed society and individual in the world are following the path of Buddha. The path of Buddha is the path of peace; the path of Buddha is an easy path of peace, following which one attains supreme happiness and peace.

Seed words: *Buddha, Buddhist, Dhamma, Peace, Path, Eightfold, Medium, Modern, and Scientific.*

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Introduction:

Many Philosophical schools have shown different paths to peace in the world. I consider Buddhism to be the best. Buddhism is not only Dhamma, but also a scientific, naturalistic, and most modern path, whose policy-determining elements are the essence of the life-research of the great man, Buddha himself. The paths shown by him are as relevant today as they were two and a half thousand years ago. I believe that all other paths are one-sided, whereas Buddha's path is the most modern, complete, and up-to-date path of peace and happiness. The diverse aspects that he thought about were not thought about by any other father of any other path or opinion, nor did he present them in completeness. Buddhism is not a religion, but a great human way of life, in which there is no place for inertia. This is a huge Peepal tree of excellence of human life, which has always been providing pure oxygen to everyone at all times without any discrimination.

I believe that whoever adopts even one branch of this path has made their life meaningful by making it

happy and peaceful. The greatest person in the world, who is searching for peace, ultimately accepts the Buddha's path. Be it Ajatashatru, Ashoka, a troubled common man, Steve Jobs, or anyone else – only the path of Buddha provides him peace and solace. The concern of this international seminar being held under the auspices of the United Nations is the spirit of world peace, which wants that after the last two world wars, the third world war does not happen again. Who knows the horrors of wars and human cruelty, and barbarity better than the earth and nature, India and Japan? Even today, the working people of India are deprived of a respectable life despite being in the land of Buddha, while every year, some country or society becomes the victim of the whims of the dictators of the world. Therefore, whether individual or collective suffering, it is the individual and nature that have to suffer. But the efforts of Buddhists, Japan, humanists, and the United Nations are continuing in this direction. Buddhism is the basis of happiness and a peaceful life. After all, what is the reason that those who want

peace see Buddha's path as the only path and no other path? Let me tell you that this article is based on my own experiences. Therefore, in this article, I will briefly discuss the peace-promoting points. So see – 'Buddha' is synonymous with intelligence – The word 'Buddha' means intelligence, and intelligence means knowledge. The one who has intelligence is knowledgeable and wise. The one who gives importance to intelligence in life is an intellectual. The intellectual one is happy.

Happiness and peace are reflected through Buddha statues – Happiness and peace are reflected through the pictures of Buddha. If you look at his picture, you will clearly understand that his picture reflects happiness, peace, and calmness. As soon as I look at his picture, I feel a sense of peace within myself. This peace and tranquillity are needed in the life of every person, and this is reflected in the pictures of Buddha. I would advise anyone seeking peace to just look at the statue of Buddha sitting in a relaxed posture and act like him – he will start feeling relaxed.

Being in the present – Buddha tells us to be in the present. It is only when moving between past and future that sorrow hurts the most. In such a situation, they say to leave the past and future and be in the present. By doing this, thoughts related to the past and future, and the sad feelings associated with them, do not come to mind. Their absence is freedom from sorrow. They say that neither the past nor the future is in the hands of a person. His only present is his own, in which he is living. Living in the present is the only guarantee of freedom from suffering. That is the moment a person has. Therefore every person should be in the present. Whatever has happened in the past has passed, that moment will never come, and why worry about the future? Who knows, you may pass before the future, or that moment may never come! In such a situation, worrying about the future is useless. Whoever has come into this world, their end is certain. In such a situation, there should not be any worry about the future; rather, the now and the present should be lived with full intensity and completeness. Overall, a person should not destroy their present by worrying about the past and future. The present is yours only. You will not gain anything by destroying it; rather,

whatever is there will also be destroyed. So, stay in the present and keep enjoying life.

Suffering is certain – Buddha says that suffering is certain, and it is certain, while there is also happiness, but the moments of happiness are few. Therefore, freedom from suffering is impossible. Yes, suffering can definitely be reduced. This is the way to live. By reducing sadness, happy moments can be experienced to the maximum extent. That is why Buddha found that suffering cannot be eliminated, but it can definitely be reduced. The good that Buddha has done for all humanity by showing the way to reduce suffering is unique. He said that the 'middle path' is the path on which every person can live their life with maximum happiness. The one who follows this path will be the enjoyer of its fruits. In such a situation, the middle path is the only path on which suffering can be reduced.

Achieving happiness and peace through the Eightfold Path – Buddha has described eight ways to reduce suffering. These roads are collectively highways, which guarantee to bring the only happiness closer and closer. If there is less sorrow, then happiness and peace will make you happy. They will give so much that you will be surprised. Therefore every person should follow the eightfold path. These are the eightfold path of Buddha –

1.Right Views : Believing in the Four Noble Truths. Believing in the Four Noble Truths, not doing violence to living beings, not stealing, not committing adultery – these are physical virtues. Apart from this, Buddha also taught the lesson of good conduct of speech, in which humans were taught not to lie, not to gossip, and not to speak harsh words. Not being greedy, not having hatred, having the right perspective - these are the good conduct of the mind.

2.Right Determination: Making a pledge for mental and moral development. Not having attachment and hatred in the mind, knowing that only a mind without attachment and hatred can concentrate, having compassion, friendship, peace, equanimity, taking a resolution not to do bad conduct (action contrary to good conduct), taking a resolution to conduct good conduct, taking a pledge to follow Dhamma.

3.Right Speech – Do not speak harmful things

and lie. Samyak speech comes in the form of practicing speaking the truth, practicing speaking sweetly, and practicing discussing Dhamma. Buddhism teaches human beings to speak quietly.

4. Right Action – Not doing harmful actions. Samyak comes at the end, practicing protection of the lives of living beings, not stealing, not committing adultery. Buddha has taught us to strictly follow non-violence for truth and justice.

5. Right Livelihood – Not doing any harmful business. To earn a livelihood through hard work, not to do five types of business, which include - trade of arms, trade of animals, trade of meat, trade of liquor, and trade of poison. By doing their business, you become the cause of loss to others.

6. Right Efforts – Trying to improve yourself. To practice following the Eightfold Path, to keep in mind the things/things that generate auspicious thoughts, to think about the ill effects of sinful thoughts, not to give space to those thoughts in the mind, to consider those thoughts as sanskars, If wrong arguments come to mind, control them, suppress them, torment them.

7. Right Mindfulness – Trying to gain the mental ability to see with clear knowledge. Kayanupasana, Vedananupasana, Chittanupassana, Dhammanupasana - all these together are called Vipassana Sadhana, which means - seeing oneself properly. To know that only a mind free from attachment and hatred can concentrate. Any person who wishes to know himself must do Vipassana. This will be the beginning of the path to relief from suffering.

8. Samyak Samadhi (Right Concentration) – To liberate oneself by attaining Nirvana. Not allowing the unborn sinful dharmas to arise, taking interest in the destruction of the born sinful dharmas, interest in the origin of the unborn efficient dharmas, and interest in the growth of the generated efficient dharmas. By following all these verbatim, life will be happy, and Nirvana (a state of eternal happiness, ecstasy, and relaxation) will be attained.

Buddha does not call it violence; it cannot be called violence. It is a cycle of natural changes, like the occurrence of day and night, the rising of the sun and the moon - all these have been happening and

will continue to happen, and many more changes can be seen in the future. Therefore, we just have to keep going without disturbing the natural laws.

Accomplishment of Ahinsa – Buddha has been the biggest, first, and strongest supporter of this world. He was in favour of maximum conservation of nature. That is why he supported non-violence and said that violence should not be done. Violence increases unnatural tendencies like anger, sadness, cruelty, barbarity, etc., and the imbalance between living beings and non-living beings increases, which increases suffering. In the world, people used to kill and eat living beings to fill their stomachs, due to which the imbalance between living beings and non-living beings was increasing; rather, human behaviour was also becoming cruel and barbaric. Due to all this, suffering was increasing, and humanity's balance with nature was deteriorating. To prevent this imbalance from worsening, Buddha had asked to stop violence. He said that nonviolence is necessary for the growth of compassion. Due to this, the person loses their natural character and turns into an animal. He has talked about stopping violence that is being done deliberately for one's benefit. It is noteworthy that there are so many things in nature that man can eat to survive, and there is no need for him to kill anyone and eat them. But man has become so lazy and parasitic that he kills and eats someone to survive. If a man wants, he can live by consuming natural things or plant-derived things. Yes, adopting violent methods to protect ourselves from some dangerous creatures is not violence. Extreme violence is real violence. For example, one can survive even by not eating chicken. One can become non-violent by eating plant-based food. The biggest loss was the imbalance of nature. That is why Buddha has described non-violence as the goal of human life, because man is a conscious being. He is more intelligent than other living beings. Actually, Buddha wanted the greatest welfare of human life. Its accomplishment was possible only through nonviolence. Violence leads to the destruction of nature, whereas non-violence maintains mutual balance between living beings and non-living beings in nature, and only by doing so can happiness, peace, and tranquillity be achieved. Overall, suffering can be reduced.

There is no God – Buddha had seen that man is also the only living being, like other living beings. He, too, is born and dies. Therefore, man is the doer; everything is his result. There is no God in the world, and there is no ruler of the world. If there were a controller, there would be no anarchy on Earth. They had seen innocent people being raped, murdered, snatched and appropriated by a powerful man. But no power or force punishes him for the said deeds. The truth is that only the violent, cruel, discriminatory, and barbaric person is happy, because he forcibly snatches the material happiness of someone, and a person consumes it himself, whereas a weak and hardworking person does not get the reward for his hard work, and he suffers only through man. It has been coined by cunning and clever people to keep people scared. This later started being used by vicious people for their benefit. In its name, people achieve dominance and live a life full of material comforts, and most people suffer sorrows. He had seen that more suffering is inflicted in the name of God in the world than in the name of anyone else, even though there is no power called God. It is a product and a means of self-fulfilment for cunning people.

Concepts like sin-virtue, heaven-hell is false – Concepts like sin-virtue, heaven-hell are deeply rooted in India. Every person in the country is suffering from this. Leaving aside his understanding and conscience, he keeps wandering from door to door to get rid of the wrath of false gods and goddesses and makes every possible effort to escape from them. The general public does not know that there is no such power as God, but the social environment has become so toxic that no one can be free from it. The people of the country are getting ruined generation after generation by getting trapped in such false notions. The person has forgotten his existence and loots everything, including his household savings. These notions have looted the general public, made them unhappy, and wasted their time more than any other. Buddha shows the way to freedom from these. They teach how to come out of them. But the general public is so trapped in the clutches of the contractors of society that they are unable to get out of it. Buddha and his Dhamma want to free them from conspiracies by telling them

the real truth of life. A person can attain peace and tranquillity only by being free from these evils. Buddhism talks about this true Dhamma.

Atta Deepo Bhava – Buddha said that ‘Atta Deepo Bhava’ means man is his lamp. He is the master of his own life. Whatever work he does, he gets the same reward. If he works as a labourer, then it is his right to get the wages. If he works, he will get bread; if he doesn't, he will get nothing. Therefore, they teach that one should not trust anyone else, and there is no need to seek refuge in anyone else. He will get what he does. Karma gets results. Therefore, he should trust himself. As soon as a person trusts himself, he feels new strength and freshness and attains peace.

Only an atheist is a true person. There are two types of people in the world: theists and atheists. Theistic or Vedantic people are theists, while people who believe in themselves are atheists. Theists have faith in someone else, whether it is a person or something else. But an atheist does not trust anyone else - be it God or a king, or anyone else. He does not trust other things of any kind. He trusts himself. He has confidence and belief in himself. As soon as he has confidence in himself, his self-confidence increases, and he makes even the most difficult tasks possible. He believes in his strength and existence. Whatever progress, destruction, and inventions have happened in the world till now, all that has been the contribution of humans, and not of any unknown power. Therefore, Buddha and his Dhamma give importance to the existence of the individual.

Practice for healing – Yoga practice ensures the mental and physical health of man. Its various physical asanas have been presented by Buddhist saints. Buddhism is a naturalistic religion. Its followers, to stay healthy for years, observed the animals, plants, and human expressions available in nature and used them on themselves and found that they were better for health. Buddhist practitioners had to stay in monasteries for years and had to go among the people and provide them with education. In such a situation, keeping the body healthy was their primary need. Only by keeping oneself healthy can a person advise or teach others to remain healthy. Therefore, Yoga is a great achievement of Buddhism. Today, the whole

world is accepting yoga as a wellness method for physical and mental health and staying healthy. This method rests on the unity of body, mind, and breath. The one who is using it in his life is the most healthy and happiest. Overall, labour and peace complement each other. Buddhist monks used to practice physical exercises for healing.

Twenty-two vows— Followers of modern Buddhism should follow the twenty-two vows presented by Baba Saheb Bhimrao Ambedkar. These twenty-two vows are the essence of the most thoughtful wisdom. These have been introduced by that great man, who has freed eighty percent of the people of India from all the shackles. They received the highest education and studied in the most developed countries in the world. He was one of the six greatest personalities of the world during his time. Modern India is his contribution. The twenty-two vows offered by such a great man are certainly going to provide freedom and peace. Therefore, I believe that anyone who wants to find peace must take these twenty-two vows. The essence of the said twenty-two vows is as follows –

- 1.I Will not believe in God, nor will I worship him.
- 2.I will not accept the concept of the incarnation of God, meaning there is no God.
3. Will not perform Shraddha and Pind Daan.
- 4.I will not perform any rites at the hands of pundits.
5. All humans are one – I will agree.
- 6.I will believe in equality.
- 7.I will follow the eightfold path of Lord Buddha.
- 8.I will follow the ten Paramitas prescribed by Lord Buddha.
- 9.I will be kind to the living beings and take care of them.
10. I will not commit theft or adultery.
11. Will not lie and will not drink alcohol.
- 12.I will try to mould my life on the three elements of Buddhism-knowledge,modesty,and compassion.
- 13.I will follow the path of Buddhism.
- 14.I will behave according to the teachings of Buddhism.2

Man is superior, and the individual is free - All ideas in the world have been created by man. Religion has also been created in the same way. But he himself has become a slave of his beliefs. In truth, man's existence lies in his freedom. He can achieve happiness

and peace only by remaining independent. God is also a gift of man. Therefore, man is the best. There is nothing and no one greater than Him. Every person is noble, free, and equal. Regarding religion B. R. Ambedkar says, "Religion is for man; man is not for religion (11)"²³.

Following the basic principles of Buddha, I think the basic principles of Buddha are very effective for one to achieve peace. Those who want peace in life must follow the basic principles of Buddha. The four principles are –

1. Man is his own master – there is no God, and neither should we believe in him.
2. Not considering the soul as eternal – it is impermanent.
3. Do not consider anyone else as an automatic proof— Only the authenticity of intelligence and experience is true.
4. Do not consider the flow of life as limited to this body only4. Life is beyond the body.

Buddha's teachings and philosophy are based on these four principles. The first three principles differentiate Buddhism from other religions of the world. These three principles are similar in materialism and Buddhism. But the fourth thing, that is, not considering the flow of life as limited to this body only, separates it from materialism, and at the same time it is a beautiful way to make the future hopeful for the person, without which it is difficult for any idealism to be transformed into a program. Rahul Sankrityayan believes that where all four are united, there is Buddha Dhamma.

Walking on the middle path - Extremism is a cause of sadness in life. Everyone has to face sorrow. But the basic objective is to avoid suffering as much as possible. Therefore, avoid overdoing it in any area. The more you avoid extremes, the more you will stay away from sorrow. That is why Buddhism is the concept of 'live and let live'. Learn from Sujata. The common woman of the village taught Buddha the middle path, and Siddhartha became 'Buddha'.

Lesson of moral strength and courage— A person who follows the path of Buddha and peace is moral. His morality is what makes him courageous. He knows that the individual is the best and the path he is walking is his path. He knows his worth. He

knows his potential and power. That is why he is a moralist. His morality is what makes him courageous because of his existence. Stories of Buddha tell us that even the cruelest king would bow before him. Even the cruel and mad elephant calmed down in front of them. Many attempts were made to kill Buddha and remove him from his path. But he was not deterred, and ultimately the bad people themselves came under his protection. Jataka tales are proof of this. Morality and courage come only when a person believes in himself. Buddha had confidence in himself. This is the reason why he could become the most moral and courageous person in this country. He had neither fear nor fear of anything. He was free from fear. We all need to learn from Buddha. We should also be moral like them. No one can be courageous without being moral. So the first condition is that you should be ethical. You should be ethical towards the person and the environment, towards nature. The more moral you are, the more confidence will increase, and as confidence increases, courage will increase. The more courage you have, the more natural you will be. This is the aim of life. Buddha teaches us to be moral and courageous. Before becoming Buddha, he also had many personal shortcomings. This is the reason why he left the house at night without informing Yashodhara. But they return home when they become Buddha.

Live and let live – Buddhism is a simplified form of ‘live and let live’. As simple as this phrase is, its meaning is not simple. In fact, at its core lies the feeling of mutual companionship between animals and nature. This companionship is the way to a happy and peaceful life. Today, forests are being cut down, and all living creatures are standing on the verge of death. He is becoming more dangerous day by day. The lifespan is decreasing. The number of causes of death is increasing day by day. He is losing his natural behavior and is becoming artificial, fake, petty, and cruel. We have to return to Buddha, attain enlightenment, only then can we implement the spirit of live and let live. We will also live, and people will also live. Our living is not only worth living, but only if everyone else also lives with us, our living will become meaningful. This should be our aim. Only by establishing enlightenment

will we be saved and save the world. We can establish enlightenment only by eliminating all the pettiness. This should be our aim and goal.

Conclusion:

Today, life has become filled with pure materialism. People are killing each other for material comforts. There have been two world wars in the last few years, and there is a possibility of a third one. Cut-throat competition based on caste, religion, region, colour, and supremacy has increased all over the world. In such a situation, Buddhism has become even more relevant. In the glare of modernity, the world has become stressed, new dangerous diseases are emerging, and the situation in the world is becoming hell-like. In such a situation, Buddha feels strongly. People seeking peace are moving to Japan and learning the natural lifestyle. Now people are turning towards forests and refreshing themselves with meditation. Migration is taking place in many countries, and many countries are facing a population shortage. At some places, there is concern about population increase, and at some places, there is concern about population decline. In such a situation, Buddha is being remembered again and again. Man has reached the peak of his development. Now he looks back and searches for peace, and Buddhism seems to be developing. Japan is a strong example of this. It is proving to be most effective in the direction of disarmament. Today, those countries are happy where Buddhism is dominant and is the way of life. We too should quickly adopt the Buddha's path, so that future destruction can be avoided and our generations can be saved.

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